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Permit Planning for Remediation of Abandoned Mine Tailings at Mount Sicker, Vancouver Island

Bell, Peter

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Abstract

This article presents an example of a permitting plan for two abandoned mine tailings sites at Mount Sicker on Vancouver Island. This paper introduces the two sites and describes possible ways to approach them together, sequentially. In addition, the paper describes different theoretical perspectives for how to set the goals for a cleanup project compared with other types of mining projects. The paper presents basic aspects of the legal framework for permitting in BC and uses them as constraints for planning the business strategy. For example, a mechanical trenching permit in BC allows 1,000 tonnes to be removed per year, which can be used to remove abandoned tailings to reduce pollution and generate geological information comparable to exploration drilling. This paper presents a permitting plan to clean up the two tailing sites and shows the locations of key work activities on Google Earth. It also presents field photographs of abandoned tailings site conditions and clay samples, which may contain relevant metals like copper, zinc, or critical minerals. The paper describes a flowsheet for this material to separate the heavy metals and leave inert waste rocks that do not cause pollution. The paper also describes methods to estimate costs for this kind of project development according to different priorities.

Keywords: Natural Resources, Industry, Environmental, Mining, Tailings, Abandoned Mine, Copper, Zinc, Critical Minerals, BC, Canada

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Q5 - Environmental Economics
Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Permit Planning for Remediation of Abandoned Mine Tailings at Mount Sicker, Vancouver Island

This article presents an example of a permitting plan for two abandoned mine tailings sites at Mount Sicker on Vancouver Island. This paper introduces the two sites and describes possible ways to approach them together, sequentially. In addition, the paper describes different theoretical perspectives for how to set the goals for a cleanup project compared with other types of mining projects. The paper presents basic aspects of the legal framework for permitting in BC and uses them as constraints for planning the business strategy. For example, a mechanical trenching permit in BC allows 1,000 tonnes to be removed per year, which can be used to remove abandoned tailings to reduce pollution and generate geological information comparable to exploration drilling. This paper presents a permitting plan to clean up the two tailing sites and shows the locations of key work activities on Google Earth. It also presents field photographs of abandoned tailings site conditions and clay samples, which may contain relevant metals like copper, zinc, or critical minerals. The paper describes a flowsheet for this material to separate the heavy metals and leave inert waste rocks that do not cause pollution. The paper also describes methods to estimate costs for this kind of project development according to different priorities.

Objective Function

There are several different ways to set the goals for how to run a mining business, depending on the theoretical framework used to determine the objectives. For example, if the business were designed to “maximize net positive impact on all future generations of the people who live around the mine site,” then that would be radically different from maximizing profits.

One possible goal is to design a business plan for this project to maximize the use of local capacity for work in all aspects. How much local business capacity exists to do something that is not currently being done? This paper focuses on plans that can be executed by local partners as much as possible. This clean-up work is highly specialized and small-scale, so it is not the typical focus for mining companies. Mining exploration companies typically focus on finding billions of dollars of metal in the ground by drilling, not processing old waste at the surface.

Another possible goal is based on the radical idea of Intergenerational Equity (Basu & Pegg, 2020). This theory suggests natural resources are like an inheritance of wealth and should not be depleted by one generation at the sacrifice of the next, which leads to ideas like increased use of sovereign wealth funds based on taxes from natural resources by countries around the world. These global ideas can also be applied at the project scale in this paper. For example, the theoretical ideas of intergenerational equity imply that it is best to clean up the abandoned tailings sites at Mount Sicker as soon as possible, using tax revenues collected by the government from other mines in BC, or maybe for the government to pay rewards to companies that clean up these abandoned sites.

Another approach is based on strict environmentalism, which would not pursue any economic recovery of metals from an abandoned tailings site. For example, we can dig up all the tailings at the site, mix them with zeolite, and then leave them to adsorb heavy minerals to reduce pollution over time. It is possible to estimate the cost of doing this kind of program and compare it to others on a cost-benefit analysis according to different theoretical frameworks and constraints.

These theoretical perspectives can provide different roles for different entities in a project like Mount Sicker. For example, we can combine ideas from Intergenerational Equity together with the profit motive, and include other priorities like “security of supply” from a national security perspective. We can use a confluence of perspectives to formulate an objective for the design of a mining exploration business relative to theoretical and practical constraints.

This paper focuses on practical permitting constraints as defined by the law in BC now. The goal is to clean up the abandoned tailings now in a way that helps advance the mining business—for example, investigating this project from the perspective of a mining exploration company or a prospector. These speculators spend risk capital on drilling to make resource estimates for the market to understand deposit size and potential. What if an exploration company were to incur the same kind of losses by advancing an abandoned mine tailings project as they do by drilling? What kind of geological information would we get for what costs?

Permitting Constraints

The practical permitting constraints in BC are described in the Mines Act (King's Printer, 2026), and the basic parameters are as follows. For a mineral claim, you can remove up to 10,000 tonnes over the life of the claim in total. To go beyond that amount requires a mineral license, which requires additional baseline environmental studies and consultation that may cost more than \$50,000 per license. The methods used in this section compare these tonnage constraints with the estimated amount of rock at two different abandoned tailings sites at Mount Sicker.

- Phase 1: Remove 1,000 tonnes per year using a Notice of Work for a mechanical trenching permit for 10 years to remove 10,000 tonnes at the COPPER CANYON tailings site.
- Phase 2: Remove 10,000 tonnes per year using a Major Mines permit for 10 years to remove 100,000 tonnes at the TWIN J tailings site.

Mine exploration financing is based on potential speculative returns. For example, a company may spend \$10 million to find a deposit with \$1 billion gross metal value; if that deposit gets a 10% market multiplier, then that's \$100 million in market value and a 10x return on the initial \$10 million investment. Cleaning up an abandoned tailings site does not find a deposit, but it does generate some geological information about the mine. It is unclear how the market would value the geological information from cleaning up a tailing site.

A secondary goal in this article is to produce as much metal as possible from the tailings, whereas the main priority is to clean up the abandoned mine tailings sites. The potential metals production is important because it represents some type of geological information about the project that is similar to a drill intercept for a mining exploration company. This paper aims to use as much local capacity for all aspects of the business development as possible and slow the pace of the cleanup work to match the local capacity to do the work, rather than bringing in expert contractors from abroad who can do the work as quickly as possible.

Furthermore, this paper includes advanced metallurgical testing to get specialized metals out of the abandoned tailings site. The technical results for these engineering studies are beyond the scope of this article, but the basic concepts are similar to the toy model in Bell (2015) that simulates the economic returns for mining exploration as a company pays for more information about the project before determining whether to build a mine or not.

Introducing the Abandoned Mine Tailings Sites

Figure 1: Local View of Abandoned Mine Tailings Sites at Mount Sicker

Figure 2: View of Current Mineral Claim Covering Abandoned Tailings Sites at Mount Sicker

Figure 3: Mount Sicker, located 10km from Port with Global Shipping Access

Figure 4: Regional view of Mount Sicker in comparison to Vancouver, BC

The Mount Sicker project, among others, was previously mined by the Canadian government for military purposes in the 1940s. McCandless (2021) provides a comprehensive review of this important episode of government funding for the mining industry in BC. This is an important example of government spending meant to maximize security of supply, not maximize profits. This longer quote describes the government investment as follows:

“During its three-year life, the Wartime Metals Corporation, guided by its advisory board, recommended subsidizing nineteen mining projects in Canada, five of which were in British Columbia. It also acted on behalf of its American counterpart, Metals Reserve Company, to use American capital to help a few Canadian mines increase their production of lead, zinc, and copper concentrate destined for American smelters. In British Columbia, with this American capital, Wartime Metals invested in restoring production at two long-closed base metal mines, subsidizing two large copper mines, and developing the Emerald tungsten mine at Salmo in the central Kootenay region. The closed mining properties were not economic by market criteria, but their proven metal reserves met Wartime Metals’ funding criteria. Similarly, copper mines received payments per pound of copper produced after satisfying the metal controller that labour shortages had raised production costs above sales revenues... the Kootenay-Florence lead zinc mine at Ainsworth; Twin J or Tyee zinc copper near Duncan; Britannia copper near Vancouver; and Copper Mountain near Princeton.” (McCandless, 2021, p. 98)

The history of Canadian mining can give us new ideas for old projects today. We can learn from the lessons of history to understand how far the mining industry has to go to meet the demand for metal in times of war. Metals are essential to development and defence for countries around the world, and Canada should be a world leader in mining. There is potential for increased government spending on mining, which can increase the security of supply and have large economic multiplier effects because primary metals production can have direct and indirect impacts that increase GDP far beyond the value of the metal production itself.

Introduction to Phase 2 “TWIN J” Abandoned Mine Tailings Site

The total weight of the tailings at TWIN J is estimated at 100,000 tonnes. This is based on a specific gravity of 2.7 and a volume of 40,000 cubic metres: greater than 3 metres deep, 100 metres long and 100 metres wide. As shown in Photograph 1, the lower wall of the TWIN J tailings pond was removed by firefighters in an emergency and never rebuilt. The pond is no longer covered with water, which has increased the ongoing pollution. It is possible to rebuild the pond and create broader containment for the area, but this has not been the focus for companies.

Photograph 1: Removed Section of Tailings Pond at TWIN J

Photograph 2: View of TWIN J Abandoned Mine Tailings Site.

One priority for project planning in this article is to build a new wall at the TWIN J tailings pond. Could we design a larger containment berm that includes things like zeolite layers to deal with the ongoing pollution that is happening now? The plan presented in this paper uses waste rock from operations of Phase 1 at the COPPER CANYON site to provide materials to build a new wall at the TWIN J site, as described in the Permit Planning section below.

Permit Planning

The details for the workflow in Phase 1 at the COPPER CANYON site are as follows:

- A. Prepare the COPPER CANYON site for work. Remove a void of rock to create a temporary storage facility for the tailings using modern pit liners and safety monitoring equipment. Use the rocks removed from the void to make a retaining wall below the tailings at the COPPER CANYON site.
- B. Dig up abandoned waste from the COPPER CANYON tailings site and move it to the temporary containment facility in Part A.
- C. Set up the processing circuit at the COPPER CANYON site and process the waste from the temporary storage. The circuit is described in Figure 5 and as follows:
 - a. Rinse down the clay.
 - b. Grind the clay.
 - c. Use gravity methods to separate the heavy metal minerals from inert rock.
 - d. Use waste rock to build a new wall at the TWIN J abandoned tailings site.
 - e. Take heavy metals away for processing somewhere else, such as advanced metallurgy facilities at the Saskatchewan Research Council.
- D. Fill the void at COPPER CANYON from part A.

The Phase 1 plan uses mechanical trenching to remove 1,000 tonnes per year. It plans to continue for 10 years to get a maximum of 10,000 tonnes at the COPPER CANYON tailings site, which is designed to maximize the basic permitting constraints and to operate at a scale that maximizes the use of local capacity for this kind of work.

The Phase 2 plan repeats this process at the TWIN J tailings site by creating a temporary storage facility, moving the tailings into it, processing the tailings to separate heavy metal minerals, and transporting the minerals offsite for metals recovery.

This plan is meant to be modular, mobile, and low-impact at the site. It is important to prioritize stabilizing the site immediately to reduce geotechnical risk before doing anything new. This approach has increased handling costs because we move material to a temporary storage facility, but it reduces pollution by getting abandoned material into containment immediately.

This plan is based on the perspective of a prospector who wants to generate the most significant geological information about the project as possible. For example, a prospector would like to know if a tailings site contained the largest amount of a certain critical metal in Canada because prospectors are focused on the promotional potential of large amounts of metal waiting to be found. These principles are designed for a local prospector who wants to bootstrap a business that could be profitable based on metal production from tailings. This paper starts with constraints on tonnage from permits, then calculates costs and potential revenues. Even with small tonnage, this project can do significant things with diverse stakeholders.

Figures 6 and 7 show the locations of the first stages of work at COPPER CANYON. This plan is unusual because it requires more development than a typical exploration program.

Figure 6: Layout of COPPER CANYON Abandoned Tailings and New Work Sites

Figure 7: Location of Processing Site for COPPER CANYON Tailings Site

The rest of this section provides further details on each step of the Phase 1 plan. The annual rate of processing for Phase 1 is 1,000 tonnes because of permitting constraints. The size of the temporary storage facility is assumed to be 2,000 tonnes to give room to handle a large amount of tailings material in advance. As in Figure 6, this is 740 cubic metres of volume at a specific gravity of 2.7. I assume this void is a circular shape with a height of 3 metres and a circular area of 250 square metres with approximately a 9-metre radius. The total size of the temporary storage facility could be much smaller if the operating plan focused on a just-in-time approach to processing tailings. For example, if the storage facility were 100 tonnes, then it could contain 10 days of material based on the assumption that the annual total is 1,000 tonnes per year with 100 days of operations. These differences would have huge implications for the cost estimates, but I start with a larger capacity storage facility to emphasize the need to contain the abandoned tailings. In practice, the permitting constraints may not allow any material to be removed to create this kind of storage facility, and the tailings may have to be piled on the surface on top of liners to prevent pollution from acid rock drainage.

Photographs 3 and 4 show examples of the clay material from the TWIN J abandoned tailings site. The material is clay, which creates significant technical challenges for processing.

Photograph 3: Example of Clay at Abandoned Mine Tailings at TWIN J Site

Photograph 4: Large Fraction of Clay at Abandoned Mine Tailings at TWIN J

This paper proposes processing methods that are “wet methods” because of the abundance of water at the site. It is possible to use dry methods that start by heating the clay to dry it before crushing and grinding. It may even be possible to use timber from the site itself to

make fires to dry the clay. However, the abundance of water at Mount Sicker is a strategic strength on a global basis in the mining industry, and this paper designs the business plan to push this local strength. The water may be useful for several things. For example, it may be possible to develop new ways to break down the clay in specialized settling ponds that submerge the clay and crush it underwater as described below. Or there may be ways to use a steam-powered engine to make electricity for the processing circuit using water and timber from the site. Or there may be opportunities to use seawater as a source of salt water to improve the separation of the clay (Sutherland, Barrett, and Gingras, 2014).

The processing circuit starts with a jaw crusher, which has a highly variable rate for clays ranging from 3 tonnes per hour to 500 tonnes per hour, depending on the clay properties such as moisture content. This project plan is considering a relatively small amount of 1,000 tonnes of tailings per year, but the jaw crusher can work very slowly, depending on the plasticity of the clay. There may be innovative ways to work the clay using lots of water. For example, what if the clay is completely submerged and put through a jaw crusher underwater? It may help to add agitators or water circulators to help break down the clay in customized settling ponds built in shipping containers and brought to the site to operate at low costs with no waste generation.

The hypothetical flowsheet in Figure 5 starts with agitation or blunging of clay to separate it into its constituent parts. This may be enough processing to allow gravity separation to separate heavy metal minerals from inert waste rock, or it may require grinding. However, it is important to leave material that does not generate acid rock drainage. It is important to do a full analysis of the geochemistry of the tailings to understand the target minerals, as in Desbarats et al. (2024). Furthermore, it is essential to recovery testwork to design a processing circuit as in Kuppusamy et al. (2024).

After agitating the clay, this paper assumes we use wet grinding methods to standardize the grain size and prepare the heavy metal minerals for separation from the gangue. A gravity concentration method, such as a cyclone, is used to separate the heavy metals from the inert rock. The inert waste rock is used to rebuild the tailing wall at the TWIN J site, while the mixed sulphides are taken off-site for processing in a controlled environment.

Figure 5: Hypothetical Flowsheet for Processing Abandoned Mine Tailings

The total size at COPPER CANYON is approximately 10,000 tonnes of tailings, where 5-10 % may report to the heavy mineral fraction. This could be only 500-1,000 tonnes of mixed sulphides over 10 years, which is 50-100 tonnes per year or 1-2 tonnes per week. This is a relatively small amount of material to be transported offsite for advanced processing, which reflects why mining companies do not pursue this strategy, because it does not capture economies of scale.

Discussion

Accurately estimating the total costs for Phase 1 requires detailed geometallurgical analysis of the tailings and assumptions about capital and operating equipment required. It is also possible to make rough estimates for the costs as follows. Phase 1 at the COPPER CANYON site entails digging up 10,000 tonnes of tailings over 10 years and using wet methods to remove heavy metals to leave inert waste. The direct mining costs could be relatively small at less than \$50 per tonne because the clay is sitting at the surface near existing logging roads. However, the

processing costs could be much higher. For example, the capital costs could be over \$1 million to build the processing circuit, get it to the COPPER CANYON site, and set it up. However, the sustaining capital costs could be relatively low at less than \$500,000 over the life of the project. Operating costs could be relatively low. The total costs could be \$2 million or \$200 per tonne for 10,000 tonnes over the entire Phase 1. Detailed engineering studies are required to determine how to do it and what it would cost, but even these rough estimates can provide a new way to determine the ongoing economic cost of the pollution: the cost of the pollution is defined in terms of how much it would cost to clean it up.

The potential gross metal value of the tailings is unknown. If the material averages 2% copper equivalent, then the gross metal value would be over \$200 per tonne and \$2 million total for 10,000 tonnes over the entire Phase 1. If the company captures all of the gross metal value, then the project could operate on a breakeven basis, but they would only get a fraction of the gross metal value if selling the mixed sulphides as a concentrate. Or they would face additional costs to refine the mixed sulphides into salable metal. The economics of a breakeven or loss-making project may not seem attractive to a profit-motivated mining company, but it is important to remember that mining exploration companies make losses when they drill. This project may have surprising strengths in the context of the exploration industry that loses money. For example, there may be a significant amount of critical minerals that further increase the gross metal value. Or the project could offer strategic advantages, such as a quick timeline to production, which is important for the security of supply.

The BC government needs to consider how the current permitting framework shapes these kinds of clean-up projects for old tailings. These projects are not widely done by companies, but the BC government may want more companies to do these projects. Are there ways to create new types of permits related to the remediation of abandoned mine sites? The current permitting framework provides a way to clean up the two abandoned tailings sites at a slow rate over a long-term horizon of 20 years. It is unclear if this approach would be profitable enough to encourage a prospector to start it or finish it. Further information is required to understand the rate of pollution now and to generate detailed estimates for the costs and benefits of cleaning up these sites.

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